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INNOVATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN FULLY DEVELOPED AND IPR CONSORTIUM GUIDELINES UPDATED

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Deliverable D2.3

Innovation and Exploitation plan fully developed and
IPR consortium guidelines updated

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PREAMBLE

The particular embodiment and funding instrument(s) for the SUNRISE Large Scale European Research Initiative are under discussion at the time of writing of this document. Due to the termination of new Flagships in Horizon Europe, SUNRISE merged with the parallel CSA ENERGY-X founding SUNERGY in early February 2020 in order to join forces towards the ambitious goals common for both CSAs. Therefore, the proposed innovation and exploitation plan and the IPR guidelines - reported here for SUNRISE - should be considered as provisional and need to be refined once the applicable boundary conditions for SUNRISE / SUNERGY are clarified.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable Report updates and details the guidelines for Intellectual Property (IP) management and the Innovation & Exploitation schemes for the SUNRISE partnership based on the previous deliverable D2.2. As outlined there, the proposed IP system on individual project level will follow the established framework for funding programs such as Horizon 2020. This implies that project partners share background IP as needed, and that newly generated IP is owned by the inventing party (or parties) with conditional access and licensing rights for other parties.

While the possibility to transfer of IP across the SUNRISE partnership is considered as beneficial in order to achieve the overall SUNRISE targets, a coercive mechanism would highly discourage private parties from participating in SUNRISE. Therefore, it is proposed that SUNRISE creates an environment which facilitates the transfer of IP on voluntary basis and that SUNRISE actively encourages IP sharing by its community members.

As far as the Exploitation plan is concerned, different approaches for Science-to-Science (S2S) and Science-to-Business (S2B) exploitation will be used – also depending on the maturity of the development activity. Key for both S2S and S2B is making information timely and consistently available – either regarding interim or final development results or regarding market or business needs and requirements. Furthermore, the failure to commercialize technology is often largely related to a poor understanding of the market. It is hence proposed that project teams are actively coached by SUNRISE in order to build their business case, and that the progress of the projects is continuously monitored in order to ensure their quality and impact, and hence their subsequent exploitability.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

SIP – SUNRISE Innovation Process

TRL – Technology readiness level

S2S – Science-to-Science

S2B – Science-to-Business

IP – Intellectual Property

IPR – Intellectual Property Rights

IPMC - IP Management Committee

H2020 – Horizon 2020

LSERI – Large Scale European Research Initiative

S&T – Science and Technology

IPMC - IP Management Committee

DESCA - Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement

MCARD – Model Consortium Agreement for Research and Development

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1. Introduction

In the previous deliverables D2.1 and D2.2, the innovation process as well as the exploitation and IPR guidelines for the SUNRISE partnership have been defined and structured. Since the transition to a circular economy - as it is envisaged in SUNRISE – is beyond the typical scale and timeline of “normal” technology development efforts, the most important task in terms of innovation is to bring fundamental research and disruptive technologies to the field through the fastest possible route and to ensure their subsequent marketability.

The key challenges here are the fact that the innovation cycles in the energy and chemical industry are often very long (particularly if innovations in material sciences are considered), that high investments are needed to bring technologies to scale (e.g. TRL 7/8 often requires the construction of new plants) which implies the risk of substantial monetary losses in the case of failure, and that products made from renewable sources are - at least at the moment – often more costly than their conventional counterparts. In order to maximize the commercial prospects of the partnership’s technology developments, the SUNRISE Innovation Process (SIP) has been defined including the concept of innovation clusters (“SUNRISE Valleys”) which provide infrastructure and a favorable innovation environment (cf. deliverable D2.1).

As far as the handling of newly generated IP along the innovation process is concerned, the guidelines on project level will follow the established practice for H2020 / Horizon Europe, whereas on partnership level, a balance between the benefits of widespread IP and information sharing on the one side and IP control for commercial partners on the other side has to be found. While making information and IP available to a large community will boost the generation of knowledge and enable new ideas and cooperation, commercial partners will not participate in such an effort without control over the IP they generate. Consequently, the partnership will struggle for impact without substantial involvement of the private sector.

Another prerequisite for the generation of impact are effective exploitation protocols, both regarding Science-to-Science (S2S) and Science-to-Business (S2B) exploitation. For the former, prompt sharing of scientific progress with others active in the research field (and preferably also in adjacent fields) based on familiar dissemination channels is required. For the latter, different methods and structures are needed to engage the business community. It is important to recognize that there is no one-size-fits-all approach for S2B, since business needs will vary depending on size, market sector and the business models. Nevertheless, it is recommended that S2B exploitation for the development of new commercial products and processes should be compatible with one of the established industry standards in product development to ensure later marketability and bankability. This implies that low-TRL activities are prepared to stop if the given requirements cannot be met, that mid-TRL activities operate in increasingly realistic environments and that high-TRL projects focus on demonstration and production-related topics and risk-reduction strategies.

2. Exploitation Plan

Following the definition of “exploitation” according to H2020 as “the use of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities”, the approach for the SUNRISE partnership should be twofold:

- **On the individual project level, the respective exploitation plans have to be in line with the overall SUNRISE roadmap which reflects the prioritized research and development directions based on multi-stakeholder feedback.**

Since the roadmap has been elaborated by the SUNRISE consortium (involving the entire SUNRISE stakeholder community) and addresses European policy makers and stakeholders from research and industry, successive short-, mid- and long-term exploitability (both S2S and S2B) will be ensured by requiring compliance of the specific project objectives with the roadmap targets. In order to achieve and maintain that accordance during the life span of a project, a continuous coaching/outreach approach to the projects should be applied in combination with a stage-gate process to review the project progress. A comparable approach has for instance been piloted for the projects awarded under call LC-SC3-RES-2-2018 (“*Disruptive innovation in clean energy technologies*”) via InnoEnergy. Accordingly, calls addressing SUNRISE targets should contain concurrent terms, for example:

“Proposals need to demonstrate a clear technology development roadmap for their solutions, including a strong exploitation plan presenting their business opportunities and impact potential.

The technological development risks need to be clearly identified and relevant mitigation measures given. Life cycle analysis shall be considered.

Projects selected under this pilot will follow a stage-gate approach based on milestones and periodic reviews. A first review by the Commission - with the help of independent experts - will take place after 12 months, based on an assessment by SUNRISE of the feasibility and innovation potential of the proposed solution or application, analyzing amongst others the business and innovation strategy, the technology readiness level of the proposed application, the consortium's freedom to operate (e.g. background, foreground, IP), and the market.

This review will lead to a first go/no go decision. Throughout the duration of the Grant Agreement, and agreed therein, SUNRISE will be involved in providing support to innovation and business development, including completing the market uptake supply chain, using external expertise, with the aim to strengthen the consortium's innovation performance.”

- On the SUNRISE partnership level, exploitability can be ensured by i) linking the SUNRISE-related projects to associated SUNRISE Valley nodes and ii) subsequently bringing together potential users / sponsors / investors with the owners of IP & know-how via the SUNRISE Valley network.

As described in deliverable D2.1, the SUNRISE Valleys are collaborative forums for discussion, exchange of information and alignment on future requirements and priorities between all stakeholders. They are organized de-centrally (so that new nodes can easily be added, for example within a newly awarded project) and provide the necessary infrastructure for fostering innovation and exploitation. In order to make the input of each node available to the entire partnership, the nodes will feed common databases (e.g. on IP, results, requirements and exploitations, categorized according to the roadmap targets) in alignment with the corresponding stakeholders to identify additional exploitation opportunities and to provide structured input for continuous updating of the roadmap. If required, the access to those databases can be restricted via a nominal fee to avoid improper use of the data. A schematic illustration of the relation between the roadmap, the projects, the nodes and the stakeholders is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Relationship between the SUNRISE roadmap, SUNRISE projects, SUNRISE Valley nodes and the SUNRISE stakeholders to enable exploitation across the partnership

It is planned to establish test pilots of the valleys during the ramp-up phase of SUNRISE (cf. also deliverable D4.2) so that a basic structure is available at the start of the planned Large Scale European Research Initiative (LSERI) and hence the exploitation on partnership level is then possible. The tasks for setting up test pilots of the valleys will comprise the study of best practices from other sectors, the identification of relevant stakeholders, a subsequent demand analysis and the evaluation of funding possibilities (based on the combination of public funding and private contributions).

Regarding the short-, mid- and long-term commercialization strategy of SUNRISE's developments, it should be kept in mind that the creation of any new business inherently requires the availability of a complete and functional technology stack. Regarding the SUNRISE roadmap, the following phases can hence be distinguished:

- Short-term commercialization will primarily focus on high-TRL technologies, e.g. PV-driven electrolysis. Since demonstrator plants and pilot plants in the multi-MW range will have to be built, there is a significant business risk due to the high capital investment needed. Hence, in order to finance such projects and bring the corresponding technologies to the market, a coordinated financial engineering for de-risking needs to be applied, which considers - in addition to the private investments - the following funding sources:
 - R&I funding (e.g. Horizon Europe)
 - Regional / national / EU structural funds (for the infrastructure-related aspects)
 - European Investment Bank (e.g. Risk Sharing Finance Facility)
 - European Fund for Strategic investment (EFSI)

Furthermore, it has to be noted that the full value chain needs to be addressed. The structure of the value chain depends on the individual topic, an example for the usage of a fuel precursor that is generated as product of electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ is given here in Figure 2. The direct product of the electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ will have no economic value, it needs to pass all further downstream process steps to become economic value as a fuel.

Figure 2: Exemplary end-to-end value chain for the electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂

When working on R&D projects it is necessary to fill all the steps of the value chain with adequate partners. They do not necessarily need to contribute with R&D at all stages (this will only be done where needed), but mandatorily need to provide the individual consortia with input on the needs and specifications of the later processing steps.

- Mid-term commercialization will be relevant for already proof-of-concept technologies (i.e. with current TRL 4 – 6), in terms of the SUNRISE roadmap e.g. for biological / biohybrid direct conversion of sunlight. The commercial exploitation of the advancements in efficiency and long-time stability will either be done by established SMEs or industrial players that can upload those results into their own product developments, or by start-up companies that carry the development further with support from early-stage investors. It is particularly important to realistically (re-)assess the viability of the business perspectives during the course of the development and to identify and involve future off-takers for those mid-TRL projects.
- For the long-term commercialization of low-TRL technologies, for example photoelectrochemical devices which enable the direct conversion of sunlight, there are understandably many uncertainties regarding the evaluation of the business potentials. While the generation of knowledge is the primary task for such projects, and the development directions might change based on new insights, it is nevertheless important to benchmark the achieved results and the future potential versus established and other emerging solutions. Such a benchmarking can be done as a part of the SIP with the aid of experts from industry, which would also support the subsequent uptake of promising results and/or an efficient re-allocation of resources. Also, this benchmarking needs to cover the whole process chain in terms of efficiency, material costs (capital expenditures), times of usage (only at daylight?), lifetime, recyclability and energy payback / energy return on invest. An example for such a value chain using photocatalytic conversion of CO₂ and to further process the intermediates to fuel is given below in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Exemplary end-to-end value chain for the photocatalytic conversion of CO₂

For reasons of practicability, more details about the SUNRISE-specific exploitation targets were included in the SUNRISE roadmap (cf. deliverable D1.2) and – as far as potential pilot customers are concerned – in the SUNRISE blueprint document (cf. deliverable D1.3), since the required techno-economical context to elucidate these aspects in deliverable D2.3 would go beyond the constraints of this report.

3. Innovation Plan

In order to achieve the required innovation performance, SUNRISE will employ the SUNRISE Innovation Process (SIP), i.e. a stage-gate approach as illustrated in Table 1 below.

Table 1: SUNRISE Innovation Process (SIP)

	Idea generation	Evaluation, Selection	Experimentation	Commercialization	Implementation
Objectives and Characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking, forums for discussion & exchange on topics related to circular economy • Provide participants with holistic view of the challenge and what their technical projects should encompass to be relevant to progressing the roadmap 	<p>Selection of projects for funding based on typical ‘call gates’:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Being within scope of a particular call ▪ Well-defined techn. challenge ▪ Clarity of desired output & impact ▪ Risk mgmt.. strategy ▪ Appropriate team with well-matched resources and tasks ▪ Logical cost basis and budget management plan ▪ Clear objectives and targets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trial, error, success, failure • SIP team will give support by providing contact point at local nodes for advice and guidance w.r.t. technical and administrative issues, arising IP, partner changes, accessing national S&T infrastructure (e.g. advanced analytical techniques) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving end-users, analyzing costs and benefits • Involving new partners and partnerships, decoupling from academic input, moving towards commercialization • Further progress depending on nature of business endeavor such as spin-offs vs. large industrial company, state and EU-level financial incentives or subsidies, fossil-fuel prices, possible market shifts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most challenging stage as the required investment levels and risks rapidly increase • Commercialization and implementation of chemical processes take time → evolutionary roll-out, first focus on local customer bases where conditions are most conducive to mitigate costs and maximize benefits • Use lessons learnt from rapid growth of renewable energy generation and electrification of drive trains
Deliverables (exemplary)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirement specifications for technology (and future products) • List of stakeholders and cooperation partners • Market potentials • Technology ideas & concepts 	<p>Proposals including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology design specification • Milestone & Review Plan • References to SUNRISE roadmap • Metrics for progress eval. • Risk assessment • Resource plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology specifications and test results • Technology capability evaluation (incl. benchmarking vs. established solutions) • Review documentation • (Scaled) Prototypes • IP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of potential markets and customers • Commercialization and financing plan • Market strategy and market entry documents • Implementation preparations (e.g. sourcing, manufacturing, validation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full-scale prototypes • Qualified systems • Requirement definitions for S&T based on operational experience • Evaluation of product operation • Identification of basic S&T

The SIP forms the overall framework for innovation management on the SUNRISE partnership level. Within the specific SUNRISE-related projects, a corresponding stage-gate methodology for project execution should be applied, cf. also chapter 2 – “Exploitation plan”.

A key element to foster innovation is a proper curriculum of trainings and seminars throughout the whole SIP in order to feed experiences and lessons learned from the implementation phase back to the earlier development stages and to feed forward findings and results from basic research to the downstream process steps. In view of the complex stakeholder structure of SUNRISE with partners from many different industries and various scientific disciplines, it is therefore planned to establish trainings and seminars along the major themes of the SUNRISE roadmap, i.e. regarding the sustainable production of hydrogen, ammonia, commodity chemicals and (jet) fuels as well as carbon capturing and long-lasting carbon storage. The trainings and seminars will be offered in three different maturation levels (i.e. basic, advanced and expert level) and shall be performed by the SUNRISE projects (as part of their dissemination protocol) with the SUNRISE valleys as platform for information sharing across the partnership.

As far as actual development protocols are concerned, the SUNRISE projects should preferably follow a development process which is compatible with established industry standards in the respective field, so that an easy exploitation and commercialization of the results is possible. Since the particular development routines differ from one industry to another and also depend on the specific development task, no one-size-fits-all approach can be applied on project level. It is therefore necessary to outline the review and gate requirements and schedule individually for each project during the project definition phase.

Furthermore, since unsuccessful exploitation and commercialization is often (partly) caused by a failure to understand the market properly, end-user requirements need to be considered already in the very early innovation stages. For a consistent (quantitative) view on the market chances of new developments across the whole SUNRISE technology development portfolio, it is considered as beneficial to have a common baseline regarding the overall market to enable an objective and transparent assessment. However, since again every SME or industrial participant in SUNRISE projects might use a slightly different market model by default, requiring the mandatory use of a particular market scenario is not regarded as practical.

A possible solution to this problem is to put the market assumptions for each project in relation to public reference scenario(s), for example the scenarios “Modern Jazz” and “Unfinished Symphony” from the World Energy Council (WEC). The reference of the individual project scope and impact to such widely accepted scenarios will be helpful in terms of attraction of investments, bankability of the technology and the alignment of research priorities with governments.

Figure 4: Baseline scenarios of the World Energy Council

(Source: http://www.worldenergy.org/assets/downloads/Scenarios_Report_FINAL_for_website.pdf, p. 13)

4. Updated IPR Guideline

General IPR guidelines for the SUNRISE partnership have already been outlined in D2.2 regarding:

- Basic IPR governance structures
- Typical IP Agreement layout
- IP Objectives

The common model contract template DESCA (c.f. <http://www.desca-agreement.eu>) for public funded projects can serve as baseline for the contractual handling of IP ownership provisions, joint ownership rules and access rights provisions, although for higher TRL projects, also other templates (like MCARD) can be used to address the specific needs of projects that are close to commercialization (e.g. regarding access rights for affiliated companies, or regarding protection periods). That means that project partners share background IP as needed, and that newly generated IP is owned by the inventing party (or parties) with conditional access and licensing rights for other parties.

In order to leverage the full potential of SUNRISE, the possibility to transfer IP across the partnership and between projects is regarded as beneficial. However, an automatic (conditional) transfer mechanism would discourage private parties from participating in SUNRISE, since they would lose control over the IP they generate. For owner-managed companies, such a mechanism would at least be undesirable (but theoretically possible if it is approved by the owner), while for corporations, it is practically impossible to consent to any default transfer of their immaterial assets without infringement of fiduciary duties.

Therefore, it is proposed that SUNRISE creates a framework which facilitates the transfer of IP on voluntary basis and that SUNRISE actively encourages IP sharing between and beyond its community members on fair conditions. The specific terms for IP sharing need to be negotiated case-by-case between the owner(s) and the user(s). To keep track of the IP information that was generated, and hence to be able to connect IP holders and potential users across the partnership, a central database should store relevant IP information (i.e. not only newly generated IP, but also results from IP reviews and clearings that were performed in the projects). The input to the database can be provided via the SUNRISE Valley nodes in alignment with the SUNRISE projects / partners, cf. also chapter 2 – “Exploitation Plan”. It should be kept in mind that such a database can primarily serve as a central IP directory for SUNRISE technologies, but in general cannot contain business information.

Finally, the ‘IP Management Committee’ (IPMC) - a SUNRISE governance body that oversees the processes of publishing, patenting, and managing the flow of S&T information into and out of the partnership - should actively promote, support and mediate the sharing of IP within the partnership when this is seen as beneficial from the partnership’s point of view. The IPMC consists of a member of each academic and industrial partner, ensuring the presence of both market, regulatory and technical experts.

The Committee will meet at least annually in the frame of a General Assembly but will conduct additional meetings whenever adequate, preferably on a half-yearly basis. More in detail, the tasks of the IPMC will be:

- Review of innovative character and exploitation potential of patentable results provided by the SUNRISE partnership
- Ensure compliance with the rules for the protection of the background and foreground IP set out in the Consortium Agreement
- Moderate potential IP discussions in order to solve issues in accordance with the Consortium Agreement
- Ensure that the knowledge disseminated follow an agreed dissemination protocol
- Support the partners in the proper protection and exploitation possibilities of IP and results.

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